

A late neolithic flint arrowhead (NVL927) from Geraardsbergen-Duitsenbroekstraat (Belgium)

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Fig. 1

1. Description and illustration

Length: 35,5 mm
Width: 17 mm
Thickness: 5 mm
Weight: 2,36 g

NVL927 is an elongated barbed-and-tanged arrowhead manufactured from fine-grained (Maisières) flint. The barbs are broken off, most likely as a result of post-depositional damage. The possibility that this artefact may represent a symbolic or status-related grave good cannot be excluded.

Fig. 2

2. Chronological/cultural attribution

A late neolithic arrowhead (3000-2000 BC).
